

Sensor Fusion for Surgical Applications

by

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ABSTRACT

The CAMIS prototype surgical navigation system combines preoperative 3d imagery and intra-operative localization to register a patient with this imagery. While this is vastly superior to the exploratory surgery that it replaced, improving anatomical localization is one of the primary goals of the CAMIS project. This presentation discusses the fusion of preoperative and intra-operative ultrasound mensuration imagery. In particular, a PC based ultrasound system developed at Washington University was modified to add localization capabilities. Then using a unique single point calibration procedure, the projection of the ultrasound 2 dimensional coordinates into full 3 dimensional patient coordinates was developed. Thus the 3d coordinates of any point in the ultrasound image can be directly calculated from this mapping.

The fusion of preoperative CT imagery with this calibrated real time ultrasound is currently being tested using a spinal phantom. A 3d CT image set of the phantom was acquired and is used as a 3d model for generating a synthetic ultrasound axial image slice. This synthetic ultrasound image was generated using the Ohio University Synthetic Ultrasound code developed under the CAMIS project. Then the spinal phantom was imaged while submerged in water and the acquisition geometry was manually aligned to get the best apparent match between the measured and synthetic ultrasound images. These two images were then computer matched by adjusting the synthetic acquisition parameters until a best match was obtained. A coordinate transformation is then shown that convert from CT coordinates to patient coordinates so that the patient and the CT image are geometrically registered through the intra-operative ultrasound image.

INTRODUCTION

In 1993 the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL, then Wright Laboratory) teamed with the Ohio Aerospace Institute (OAI), the Cleveland Clinic (CCF), and Picker International (PI) to develop the Computer Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery (CAMIS) system. One of the initial goals of the project was to involve military hospitals in the project clinical evaluation so that this new technology could benefit the military health care system. Therefore, the Wright Patterson Medical Center was added to the team and prototype CAMIS systems were later installed at the medical center as well as at the Air Force Wilford Hall Medical Center and the Army Madigan Medical Center. There also are three Universities participating in the project and they are Washington University, Wright State University, and Ohio University.

The AFRL interest in the project was to apply Air Force technologies to medical applications. The primary technology that has been pursued has been sensor fusion and navigation. These technologies are being developed by the Air Force to help the pilot find, identify, and attack his targets for "surgical strike" operations. These missions require extreme accuracy so that the target can be destroyed while minimizing collateral damage. A future scenario is that as an attack aircraft approaches an enemy zone, long range synthetic aperture radar (SAR) images of the area are formed and on board computers analyze these images to detect possible targets. Any detections are further analyzed by determining their geolocation and directing on board infrared cameras (FLIR) to image these locations as they come into viewing range. Computer automatic target recognition (ATR) algorithms further classify these detections as false alarms or as targets and the pilot is prompted with the analysis results and the collected images. The computer ATR algorithms cannot detect and identify the targets with either single sensor, but by fusing their information they will be able to help the pilot attack targets he would have otherwise missed. The SAR image contains information for detecting targets at long ranges and for calculating additional target information such as positions, ranges, and orientations. This additional information enables the ATR

algorithms to reacquire these targets in the FLIR images, to recognize the targets, and to further refine their geolocation.

The surgeon faces a similar "mission" while performing cranial surgery. The CAMIS system displays the magnetic resonance imagery (MRI) to detect, identify, and locate the tumors within the brain and to record the surgeon's planned surgical path to the tumor. His approach is such that he will minimize the damage to essential brain centers and to avoid cutting critical blood vessels. During surgery, the CAMIS system displays the imagery and provides precise navigation into the skull and brain and along the planned path to the tumor. After the difficult task of getting to the tumor is complete, the surgeon needs to begin extracting the tumor. However, the tumor is difficult to visualize because there is virtually no contrast between brain and the tumor. Therefore the surgeon depends on the navigation ability of the CAMIS system to determine what to extract to ensure that the total tumor is removed.

CAMIS PROTOTYPE SYSTEM

The CAMIS navigation system begins with the preoperative MRI. The patient is imaged with three to eight fiducial beads glued to the scalp and these beads remain on the patient until surgery. These beads appear as bright points in the MRI and part of the surgical planning is to locate the 3 dimensional (3d) position of each bead in the MRI. Then, prior to surgery, the patient's head is locked into a fixed position and the CAMIS localizer is used to measure each bead's 3d position within the operating room and at the same time determine the corresponding bright point in the MRI. The CAMIS system uses the 3d position of the beads in the MRI and in the operating room to determine the geometric transformation matrix that relates any point in the MRI to the surface or the inside of the patients head. Once this transformation is determined, the beads are removed and the surgeon begins the surgery. This transformation matrix and the localizer enable the surgeon to determine location of his planned entry point on the patients head and to follow the planned path to the tumor.

The original CAMIS localizer consisted of four miniature microphones mounted at the corners of a square panel and a two miniature spark gaps located on a pointer. As a spark generates an impulsive sound, the time of flight of the sound between a spark gap and each microphone is used to calculate the spark gap's position relative to the four microphones. Since the position of each spark gap along the straight of the pointer is known, the position and orientation of the tip can easily be calculated.

A second application of the computer aided surgical navigation system is to assist in the placement of pedicle screws. The pedicle is a thin region of the spinal vertebrae next to the spinal cord. Therefore, this placement must be very accurate in both position and angle so that the screw can be securely placed in the pedicle region and safely away from the spinal cord. In this case, instead of using beads as fiducial points, the tips of the lateral and spinal processes of the vertebrae are located both in the CT imagery and on the patient. After registering the patient to localizer system and calculating the registration transformation matrix, the surgeon tactilely locates the entry point and orientation for the screw. Then, he compares his estimates with his pre-planned position and orientation values using the CAMIS localization system. If they agree, he then places the screw. If not, he reevaluates his tactile estimates and his registration of the localization system until he get precise agreement between the two desired screw locations. As successful as this tactile and computer based approach has been, it is still a very invasive procedure. The use of ultrasound is being considered to enable percutaneous insertion of the pedicle screws.

CAMIS SENSOR FUSION

The CAMIS prototype equipment has enhanced both surgical applications described above. Further enhancements are being developed by fusing the preoperative imagery with intra-operative ultrasound. In the case of the craniotomy, the preoperative MRI limits the accuracy of the single sensor approach. The preoperative MRI of the patient is acquired the day before surgery and usually with the patient on his back. During surgery, the patient will be orientated to facilitate the surgery often on his side or stomach.

Since the brain is floating in cerebral spinal fluid (CSF) and since once the skull is opened the brain swells, there is a shift and change of scale between the patient and the preoperative imagery. The errors caused by these factors combined with the measurement error of the localizer and spatial errors of MRI limit the accuracy of the actual localization to between one half to one centimeter. However, this is still much better than previous approaches used for cranial surgery.

The proposed solution to this registration error is to use an intra-operative sensor such as an ultrasound along with the MR or CT imagery. Figure 1a shows an MRI of a tumor of a patient at WPMC and figure 1b

Figure 1a. Preoperative MRI of a tumor.

Figure 1b. Intra-Operative Ultrasound of Tumor.

shows an ultrasound image of the same tumor taken during surgery. If the ultrasound is calibrated such that the 3d location of each pixel of the ultrasound image is known and the correspondence between the ultrasound imagery and the MRI known, then the ultrasound used intra-operatively can provide the brain shift parameters. However, this requires matching a 2d ultrasound image with a 3d MRI or CT image. In general, performing such a cross phenomenology correlation is difficult. Instead of directly matching the ultrasound image with the CT or MR image, the CT or MR image can be used as a 3d model of the patient. Then synthetic ultrasound generation software can use this model to form a synthetic ultrasound image of the patient which in turn can be matched with the measured ultrasound to determine the brain shift parameters. This synthetic ultrasound generation software was written by Ohio University in collaboration with AFRL and sponsored by the CAMIS project.

Ultrasound also is being developed to enhance the registration process for pedicle screw placement. The use of ultrasound might enable the percutaneous insertion of the pedicle screws which would considerably reduce the invasiveness of the procedure. Even if the invasiveness can not be reduced, ultrasound registration can improve the accuracy and speed of registration.

ULTRASOUND CALIBRATION

A Washington University ultrasound system was modified to use four spark gaps for localization of the ultrasound head. In order to extend the localization down to the ultrasound pixel level, a special calibration procedure was developed using a plastic pin head. The ultrasound head is positioned such that the pin head is imaged at a specific coordinate of the image (figure 2).

Figure 2. Single point imaging.

If $p(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z})$ is the 3d position of the pin head then

$$p(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z}) = p_0(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z}) + \tilde{x}'\mathbf{v}_1 + \tilde{y}'\mathbf{v}_2 + \tilde{z}'\mathbf{v}_3$$

where $p_0(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z})$ is the spark gap measured origin of the local coordinate system

\mathbf{v}_1 points up through the center of the ultrasound head,

\mathbf{v}_2 points in the direction of the dot on the head of the ultrasound,

\mathbf{v}_3 is normal to the first two vectors .

$\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z}$ are in the microphone coordinate system

and $\tilde{x}', \tilde{y}', \tilde{z}'$ are in the moveable spark gap coordinate system.

This can be represented in matrix form by

$$\begin{pmatrix} -\tilde{x}_0 \\ -\tilde{y}_0 \\ -\tilde{z}_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & v_{1x} & v_{2x} & v_{3x} \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & v_{1y} & v_{2y} & v_{3y} \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & v_{1z} & v_{2z} & v_{3z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{x} \\ \tilde{y} \\ \tilde{z} \\ \tilde{x}' \\ \tilde{y}' \\ \tilde{z}' \end{pmatrix}$$

By imaging this point $p(\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}, \tilde{z})$ at two or more unique orientations (figure 2) of the ultrasound being careful to insure that the point is in the same ultrasound image location (l, θ) , then the unknowns $\tilde{x}', \tilde{y}', \tilde{z}', \tilde{x}, \tilde{y}$, and \tilde{z} can be estimated by augmenting the above matrix form.

The plane of the ultrasound is then identified by performing the above procedure on several points within

Fig 3. Determining the Ultrasound Plane

the ultrasound (Figure 3) and fitting a plane to the set of $\bar{x}', \bar{y}', \bar{z}'$ points yielding a plane

$$a\bar{x}'_i + b\bar{y}'_i + c\bar{z}'_i + d = 0$$

By rotating and translating the coordinate system of the plane, the above plane can be reduced to a 2d coordinate system \bar{x}, \bar{y} . This transformation is

$$\begin{pmatrix} \bar{x} \\ \bar{y} \\ \bar{z}_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\phi) & 0 & -\sin(\phi) \\ \sin(\alpha)\sin(\phi) & \cos(\alpha) & \sin(\alpha)\cos(\phi) \\ \cos(\alpha)\sin(\phi) & -\sin(\alpha) & \cos(\alpha)\cos(\phi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{x}' \\ \bar{y}' \\ \bar{z}' \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ d_0 \end{pmatrix}$$

with

$$\tan(\phi) = \frac{a}{c}$$

$$\tan(\alpha) = \frac{-b}{a\sin(\phi) + c\cos(\phi)}$$

and d_0 is the value of d when the vector $(a, b, c)^T$ is normalized. Then for any point $(\bar{x}', \bar{y}', \bar{z}')^T$ in the plane the value \bar{z}_0 in the above equation is zero.

The next requirement is to fit the range-angle coordinates (l, θ) from the ultrasound image of each of the points used to form the plane to the \bar{x}, \bar{y} coordinates of the plane. This is done by fitting the rectangular \hat{x}, \hat{y} coordinates of the ultrasound image

$$\hat{x} = \hat{x}_0 + (l + l_0) \cos(\theta + \theta_0)$$

and
$$\hat{y} = \hat{y}_0 + (l + l_0) \sin(\theta + \theta_0)$$

where

l_0 is the distance from the ultrasound crystal offset,

θ_0 is the angular offset within the plane,

and \bar{x}_0, \bar{y}_0 is the local coordinates of the ultrasound crystal.

to the \bar{x}, \bar{y} by minimizing the error

$$e = \sum_i (\hat{x}_i - \bar{x}_i)^2 + (\hat{y}_i - \bar{y}_i)^2$$

summed over the measured points that were used to determine the plane of the ultrasound.

At this point the three dimensional coordinates of any point in the ultrasound image can be calculated. The ultrasound rectangular coordinates \hat{x}, \hat{y} are first rotated about the origin normal to the plane of the ultrasound and then translated by \hat{x}_0, \hat{y}_0 using

$$(1) \quad \begin{pmatrix} \bar{x} \\ \bar{y} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{x}_0 \\ \hat{y}_0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) & 0 \\ \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \hat{x} \\ \hat{y} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Rotating back to the unrotated ultrasound image is then done with:

$$(2) \quad \begin{pmatrix} \bar{x}' \\ \bar{y}' \\ \bar{z}' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\phi) & \sin(\alpha)\sin(\phi) & \cos(\alpha)\sin(\phi) \\ 0 & \cos(\alpha) & -\sin(\alpha) \\ -\sin(\phi) & \sin(\alpha)\cos(\phi) & \cos(\alpha)\cos(\phi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{x} \\ \bar{y} \\ -d \end{pmatrix}$$

and rotating and translating back to the patient coordinates is by:

$$(3) \quad \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{x} \\ \tilde{y} \\ \tilde{z} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_{1x} & v_{2x} & v_{3x} \\ v_{1y} & v_{2y} & v_{3y} \\ v_{1z} & v_{2z} & v_{3z} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \bar{x}' \\ \bar{y}' \\ \bar{z}' \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{x}_0 \\ \tilde{y}_0 \\ \tilde{z}_0 \end{pmatrix}$$

SYNTHETIC ULTRASOUND TRANSFORMATION

In order to develop the transformation from 3d imagery to microphone based coordinates synthetic ultrasound imagery is iteratively produced to until the best match between measured and synthetic ultrasound images is produced. The parameters of the synthetic generation form the desired transformation from ultrasound coordinates to 3d imagery in homogeneous coordinates which is

$$(4) \quad \begin{pmatrix} x_{CT} \\ y_{CT} \\ z_{CT} \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u_x & w_x & n_x & O_x \\ u_y & w_y & n_y & O_y \\ u_z & w_z & n_z & O_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_{SU} \\ y_{SU} \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

where

the origin of the ultrasound image in CT coordinates is $O_p = (O_x, O_y, O_z)^T$

the normal to the synthetic image in CT coordinates is $N_p = (n_x, n_y, n_z)^T$

the direction of the ultrasound probe in CT coordinates is $U_p = (u_x, u_y, u_z)^T$

and the cross direction is CT coordinates is $W_p = (w_x, w_y, w_z)^T$

which is the cross product

$$W_p = N_p \times U_p.$$

MATCHING TRANSFORMATION

The final transformation required to transform CT coordinates into microphone coordinates is the matching transformation. This is really a compensation for incorrect parameters being used in the synthetic generation. Ideally, this transformation is a diagonal matrix but may involve a scale, rotation, and translation all in 2d until the matching and synthetic generation iterations complete.

The method of registering 3d imagery to ultrasound is demonstrated below. A phantom lumbar spine was imaged in the CT at the Wright Patterson Medical Center. A 3d rendition from that imagery is shown in figure 4a. A cross section of that imagery is shown in figure 4b.

Figure 4a. Spinal Phantom from CT imagery.

Figure 4b. Cross section of Spinal Phantom.

The phantom was submerged in a container of water and imaged with a laboratory ultrasound (Figure 5a.). Then the imaging parameters were estimated and a synthetic ultrasound was generated and compared with the measured image. Then the parameters were manually searched until a matching synthetic ultrasound (Figure 5b.) was found. These ultrasound images are shown superimposed in figure 5c.

Figure 5a. Measured Ultrasound Image

Figure 5b. Synthetic Ultrasound Image

Figure 5c. Superimposed Ultrasound Image

The total coordinate transformation from CT coordinates to patient (or microphone) coordinates is the sequential application of the inverse of equation (4), then equation (1), then equation (2), and finally equation (3). These can all be put into homogeneous coordinate form such as equation 4 and all multiplied together for a single transformation matrix.

is much better than its predecessor. Using sensor fusion, the 3d structure of the preoperative CT imagery can be combined with the location information of the intra-operative ultrasound. Currently, the calibration of the ultrasound and the coordinate transformation from the measured ultrasound to the patient coordinates have been tested with a limited amount of laboratory data. The accuracy seems to be within 2 millimeters. The synthetic ultrasound and matching code was developed by Dr. Dave Chelberg at Ohio University and was tested by AFRL yielding the matching results shown. The next phase is to automate the matching and to use multiple measured synthetic images instead of just the single image as shown.

James David Leonard; Jr.

Mr. Leonard is currently the Technical Director of the Reference Systems Branch of the Automatic Target Recognition Division of the Sensors Directorate. This branch develops Global Positioning System (GPS) technologies to ensure robust navigation availability in a hostile environment. As part of this development, several Micro Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS) projects are developing on chip accelerometers and gyroscopes. This assured reference information is also applied to support sensor fusion and automatic target recognition activities in the division.

Mr. Leonard is also the Air Force lead of the Computer Assisted Minimally Invasive Surgery (CAMIS) project with the Cleveland Clinic Foundation, Picker International, Ohio Aerospace Institute, and the Wright Patterson Medical Center. In this project he has developed sensor fusion algorithms for preoperative CT and intra-operative ultrasound. This effort is intended to provide the neurosurgeon intra-operative navigation accounting for rotation and shifting between preoperative imaging and surgery.

Previously, Mr. Leonard developed Automatic Target Recognition algorithms for identifying aircraft type from air-to-air radar signatures, lead algorithm developments for sensor fusion of Laser Radar and thermal imaging Flir, and on Synthetic Aperture Radar Recognition algorithms for identification of targets in high clutter scenes. He has lead several research efforts utilizing artificial neural networks for target recognition and is experienced in digital and analog circuit design, digital integrated circuit design, and computer programming.

Mr Leonard participates in several national defense and technical organizations. He is the previous government chairperson of the technology committee of the Automatic Target Recognition Working Group and has published several papers and given presentations on Automatic Target Recognition, CAMIS, Laser Radar, and Artificial Neural Networks for image based recognition.

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BEE	The Ohio State University 1970
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